

Supporting Information:

Design of a Chlorophyll Fluorescence Sensor Head for Continuous On-Leaf Measurements

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- KiCAD production files for the flexible PCB
- Corresponding bill of materials
- 3D printing files for mechanical components
- Videos of pull force tests (mechanical characterization)
- Video of sensor deployed in a forest under strong wind